

PREVENTING, SUPPRESSING, STOPPING, DETECTING AND SOLVING CRIMES IN OPERATIONAL-SEARCH ACTIVITIES IS THE MAIN TASK IN ENSURING HUMAN RIGHTS AND FREEDOMS

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Annotation. The author's definition of these concepts was developed based on the opinions of specialists on the essence and content of such concepts as prevention, suppression, arrest, detection, and disclosure of crimes in ensuring human rights and freedoms in the operational-search activities of the internal affairs bodies, as well as the study of the experience of the USA, Great Britain, Belgium, France, Germany, Canada, and Japan.

Key words: human rights, prevention, suppression, arrest, detection, and exposure of crimes.

It should be noted that in order to fully ensure human rights and freedoms in the operational-search activities of the internal affairs bodies, employees of bodies carrying out operational-search activities are required to conscientiously fulfill such tasks as prevention, suppression, arrest, detection, and disclosure of crimes provided for by Law No. 344 "On Operational-Search Activities." First and foremost, it is necessary to study the opinions of specialists and the experience of states regarding the essence and content of these theoretical concepts.

According to A.V. Petrenko, "crime prevention is the activity of identifying the causes and conditions that allowed crimes to be committed, preventing crimes, as well as preventing the influence of persons who have committed illegal actions, which includes measures of a general social and special criminological nature, which means a broader meaning than the concept of crime prevention" [308].

T.A. Bogolyubova argues that "the strategy of crime prevention is related to the concept of "prevention," "elimination," while the concept of "prevention" is a tactic of crime prevention."

R.V. Zhubrin defines "comprehensive activities of state authorities and local self-government bodies, state and municipal control bodies, legal entities and individuals to reduce the risk of committing crimes by identifying, eliminating (preventing), and preventing factors of crime within their competence as a set of systematic and interconnected measures" [260].

Some experts believe that concepts such as "crime prevention," "crime prevention," "crime prevention," and "crime prevention" are synonymous concepts close to each other in content, while most experts believe that the concept of "crime prevention" is correct in theory and practice. Many criminologists believe that "crime prevention is the most effective method than other methods."

Over the past two decades, the theory and practice of crime prevention have developed in Western European countries, including the United Kingdom, Belgium, France, and Germany, and a number of practical and systematic measures have been implemented to

prevent crime. There are two levels of crime prevention in EU member states. These are: social and situational situations. Social crime prevention focuses on changing unfavorable conditions, especially the microenvironment, for the formation of a person's personality.

2. In crime prevention in situational situations, a certain category of criminal actions arises in certain conditions, at certain times and in certain places, for example, when a mass event is held in public places, and crime prevention is achieved through the correct use of force and means in this situation.

There are three levels of crime prevention in the Federal Republic of Germany. These are:

- 1) Social and economic factors are studied as the causes of crimes;
- 2) by explaining the essence and content of legal measures of influence by police bodies;
- 3) the application of the type of punishment established by law.

In the prevention of organized crimes (such as abuse of power, bribery), there is a need to constantly improve the system of preventive measures [264; 270 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Many European countries have established national councils for crime prevention, the main functions of which are:

- 1) assessment of programs for information collection, planning, implementation, and crime prevention;
- 2) coordination of the activities of the police and other bodies working in this area;
- 3) ensuring public participation;
- 4) cooperation with the media;
- 5) conducting research;
- 6) cooperation with legislative bodies that determine policy in the field of combating crime;
- 7) Organization of a training seminar on crime prevention.

In the UK, minimum rules for organizing security in administrative areas have been developed to prevent crime. Measures such as the implementation of patrol service by the population in cooperation with the police, that is, the organization of duty in criminogenic areas, are widely used, and representatives of this public are provided with special technical means (handcuffs, radio communication devices, cars) for the effective performance of the service [329]. The primary function of the police service is the prevention of crime, with subsequent functions consisting of the effective investigation and disclosure of crimes.[333]

In the United States, three models of crime prevention have been developed: the model of public institutions, the model of personal safety, and the model of influence through the environment. In some states, the participation of citizens in strengthening law and order allows for the prevention of nearly 30% of theft, and as a result of operational-search prevention, citizens who provide meaningful information are financially rewarded.[247, p. 87; 253, p. 275).

In Canada, the involvement of citizens in the patrol service in the administrative territory is effectively organized, and the conduct of patrol by citizens together with police officers directly increases their sense of fear of those who commit crimes and teaches them to serve responsibly. Additional posts will also be established in areas where crimes are most frequently committed at night. In crime prevention, police criminologists study the causes and

conditions that allowed crimes to be committed, develop proposals and recommendations for improving police activities, and actively participate in the development of crime prevention plans, cooperation with government agencies, non-governmental and non-profit organizations [228, p. 34].

Crime prevention in Japan is divided into four systems. These are:

1) a crime prevention system that encompasses all spheres of public life; 2) a system of state preventive measures developed on the basis of a specific goal; 3) a system of institutional control at the state and municipal levels; 4) a system of measures for the early prevention of crimes and the prevention of repeated crimes [217]. Criminologists argue that crime prevention is not only a situation that affects specific criminogenic factors, but also a social phenomenon that requires constant study. Therefore, these levels, models, and systems of crime prevention are the most effective way to combat crime. Overall, the study of models, forms, and methods of crime prevention used in foreign countries (Germany, the United States, Canada, the United Kingdom, and Japan) allows for judgments about the adequate provision of members of all segments of society in this activity, the constant assistance of citizens to police officers.

In our view, the primary goal of crime prevention should be aimed at preventing any harm caused or likely to be caused to individuals, society, and the state. Based on the opinions of the aforementioned specialists and best foreign practices, we define the theoretical concepts that constitute the main tasks and functions of operational-search activities in defining our personal point of view as follows:

crime prevention in operational-search activities is a system of general measures aimed at adapting individuals prone to committing crimes to social life, preventing the commission of new crimes by authorized state bodies in cooperation with civil society institutions and other state bodies;

Crime prevention in operational-search activities - a set of measures to put an end to subsequent criminal activities by officials of authorized state bodies by stopping the actions of a person preparing, planning, committing a crime;

Termination of crimes in operational-search activities - measures aimed at stopping subsequent actions of a person as a result of external influence by officials of authorized state bodies before the commission of a crime (arrest of accomplices, seizure with evidentiary items on the way to the scene of the crime, on the way);

Crime prevention in operational-search activities is a system of organizational and tactical, special measures aimed at early prevention of crimes committed by officials of authorized state bodies or possible future crimes;

Detection of crimes in operational-search activities - measures aimed at identifying a socially dangerous act committed on the basis of an application or report received by authorized state bodies, officials;

The disclosure of crimes in operational-search activities is the process of identifying and fully proving the act of a person (persons) who has committed a socially dangerous act based on an application or report received by officials of authorized state bodies

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